

EFFICACY AND SAFETY OF Q-SWITCHED Nd: YAG LASER IN FACIAL MELANOSSES IN TERTIARY CARE CENTRE: A PROSPECTIVE EPIDEMIOLOGICAL STUDY

Dr.P.V. Sai Gireesh¹, Dr.M. MADHAVI LATHA², Dr. T. PRAVEENA³

¹final year post graduate, ²Prof and Head of the department, ³Professor

¹Department of DVL,

¹Santhiram Medical College and General Hospital, Nandyal, AP, INDIA-518501

Abstract: BACKGROUND: Hypermelanoses involving predominantly face and neck is relatively common with significant cosmetic disfigurement and psychosocial impact. Altered facial pigmentation can be black, blue or brown in colour depending upon the distribution of melanin pigmentation. Q-switched Nd: YAG laser is effective in resistant facial melanoses.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES: To determine the Efficacy and safety of Q-Switched Nd: YAG laser in treatment of various facial melanoses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: Total of 60 patients were treated with Q-Switched Nd: YAG laser with spot size 4-6mm, fluency 2.5-3.4 J/cm², frequency 5-10 Hz for 6 sessions. A detailed clinical history and examination were done. Standardized global photographs taken using digital camera before each laser session and end of 3 months. Clinical improvement was assessed according to physicians global assessment and side effects are noted.

RESULTS: Majority of patients had post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (n=37) followed by Melasma (n=13) Freckles (n=5), Nevus of Ota (n=3), Lichen Planus Pigmentosus (n=2). On comparison of pigmentation from the baseline, 56% of patients showed moderate improvement, slight improvement was seen in 33% of patients, while 28% experienced no improvement. Adverse effects such as transient burning sensation, pain, erythema occurred in 10 patients of Post-Inflammatory Hyperpigmentation and 5 patients of Melasma, Mottled hypopigmentation observed in 1 patient of Nevus of Ota.

CONCLUSION Q-switched Nd: YAG laser is safe and effective mode of treatment for pigmented lesions. The QS-Nd: YAG laser is effective and worth trying in conditions such as PIH, Melasma and freckles. The response after multiple sessions was variable in Freckles, Naevus of Ota. Adjunctive measures to maintain this response need to be explored in the near future.

KEYWORDS: Q-Switched Nd: YAG Laser, facial melanoses, melasma, PIH,

INTRODUCTION

Disorders of pigmentation causing considerable social and psychological distress to patients are often encountered in clinical practice. Pigmentary conditions can be classified based on the location of pigment as epidermal, dermal and mixed epidermal-dermal lesions(1). Cutaneous hyperpigmentation is a frequent complaint constituting 8.5% of all dermatological consultations(2). The color of an individual's skin is generally determined by the number of chromophores, namely melanin, hemoglobin and carotenoids (3). Hyperpigmentation of skin is usually caused by excess production and/or clumping of the melanin pigment(4). Pigmentation, especially on the face may cause significant emotional and psychological distress(5). Melasma, freckles, post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation are some of the common pigmentary conditions seen in daily clinical practice. Various modalities of treatment are used for facial pigmentation with varying results, and the condition remains difficult to treat, particularly as the treatment modalities themselves may lead to hyperpigmentation and worsening of the condition.

The QS-Nd: YAG laser delivers extremely high energy in a very short pulse. The use of laser toning mode with 1064 nm has enhanced the safety of this laser. Despite the availability of this laser for over a decade, very few publications are available concerning Indian patients. This publication seeks to fill this void by documenting the data regarding QS-Nd: YAG laser use on Indian patients, among whom hyperpigmentation is a very common and cosmetically disturbing condition.

In this study, Efficacy and side effect profile of Qs-Nd: YAG laser treatment for Facial melanoses have been assessed.

I. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES.

To study the efficacy and safety of Q-Switched Nd: YAG laser in treatment of various facial melanoses.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethical clearance by Institutional ethics committee. This study is a prospective study with a sample size of 60 where patients who were willing to participate in the study and willing to give written informed consent presenting to DVL OPD at private medical college and general hospital conducted between June 2023 to December 2023, patients who are refractory to medical treatment are included in our study. Patients who are not willing to participate and give written informed consent, patients with unstable vitiligo and psoriasis for risk of koebnerization of treated area, patients with photo-aggravated cutaneous conditions(SLE),exfoliating procedures in the last 3 months or surgical procedures within the last year, hypersensitivity to light(visible and infrared),anticoagulant and immunosuppressant treatments, pregnancy and lactation, keloids, personal or family background of skin malignancy, undergone previous laser or light treatments for removing hyperpigmentation were excluded in our study. standardized global photographs taken before and after each laser session of total 6 sessions with each session gap of 1 month. Topical EMLA (Eutectic Mixture of Lignocaine and Prilocaine) cream applied 45minutes prior to the procedure.1064 Q-Switched Nd: YAG laser hand piece was held perpendicularly and laser pulses given with minimum overlap to cover entire area. According to the type of Pigmentation, the fluency and spot size will vary. Usual parameters-Spot size 6mm, Fluency 2.5-3.4 J/cm², Frequency 5-10 Hz. Immediate mild erythema was the end point. Post-Procedure care was done by applying ice packs followed by moisturizer and Sunscreen with SPF 50.

PHYSICIANS GLOBAL ASSESSMENT (6)

SCORE	DESCRIPTION
0	Clear, except for possible residual discoloration (>90%)
1	Almost clear/very significant clearance (75-90%); only minor evidence of hyperpigmentation remains
2	Marked improvement/significant improvement (50-75%); some disease evidence of hyperpigmentation remains
3	Moderate improvement, intermediate between slight and marked improvement; 25-50% improvement in appearance of hyperpigmentation.
4	Slight improvement/some improvement (1-25%); significant evidence of hyperpigmentation remains
5	No improvement; hyperpigmented condition unchanged
6	Worse; condition worse than at week 0

II. RESULTS

In the current study, a total of 70 patients were included in the study, of which 50 were female and 20 were male. Most of the patients had post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH) (n = 37), followed by melasma (n = 13), freckles(n=5), Naevus of Ota (n=3), lichen planus pigmentosus (n=2).

FACIAL MELANOSSES TYPES	NUMBER OF PATIENTS
POST INFLAMMATORY HYPERPIGMENTATION	37
MELASMA	13
FRECKLES	5
NEVUS OF OTA	3
LICHEN PLANUS PIGMENTOSUS	2

Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation. Thirty-seven PIH patients of age group 17- 28 years were included in the study, of which 3 (8%) showed 50-75% improvement, 17 (45 %) showed 25-50% improvement, 9 (24%) had 1-25% improvement. No change in pigmentation was noted in eight (21%) patients. Transient burning sensation, erythema and pain noticed in 10 patients.

Score 2	3 patients
Score 3	17 patients
Score 4	9 patients
Score 5	8 patients

BEFORE

AFTER

SCORE 2

SCORE 2

SCORE 3

Melasma. Thirteen patients of melasma of age group 28-40 years were included in the study. Improvement of 1-25%

was seen in four (30 %) patients, while seven (53%) had improvement between 25-50%. No improvement in pigmentation was noticed two (15%) patients. Transient burning sensation, erythema and pain noticed in 5 patients.

score 3	7 patients
score 4	4 patients
score 5	2 patients

BEFORE

AFTER

SCORE 3

SCORE 3

SCORE 4

Freckles Five patients of age group 15-28 years were included in the study. Moderate improvement was seen in 1 patient, slight improvement was seen in 2 patients, no improvement in pigmentation was noticed in 2 patients.

score 3	1 patient
Score 4	2 patients
score 5	2 patients

BEFORE

AFTER

SCORE 3

SCORE 4

Naevus of ota

Five patients of age group 20-25 years were included in the study. slight improvement was seen in 3 patients, no improvement in pigmentation was noticed in 2 patients. Mottled hypopigmentation observed in 1 patient of Nevus of Ota.

score 4 | **3 patients**

score 5 | **2 patients**

BEFORE

AFTER

SCORE 4

BEFORE

AFTER

SCORE 5

Lichen planus pigmentosus Two patients of age group 20-30 years were included in the study. No improvement in pigmentation noticed in 2 patients.

SCORE 5 – 2 PATIENTS

BEFORE

AFTER

Most of the patients (90%) had no side effects, proving the safety of the QS-Nd: YAG laser in the treatment of pigmentary lesions. The side effects noted were transient burning sensation, erythema and pain noted in 10 patients of post inflammatory hyperpigmentation, 5 patients of melasma which subsequently improved during follow-up without any treatment.

Burning sensation Erythema Pain	10 patients of PIH
Burning sensation Erythema Pain	5 patients of Melasma
Mottled hypopigmentation	1 patient of Naevus of Ota

Satisfaction levels of 50 % or more were seen in 40 % of patients, whereas 60 % of patients had < 50% satisfaction. On the physician’s global assessment, 56% of patients showed 50% or more improvement in pigmentation, whereas 33 % had less than 50% change in pigmentation from the baseline level. No response was seen in 28 % of patients from the baseline.

MODERATE IMPROVEMENT	56% PATIENTS
SLIGHT IMPROVEMENT	33% PATIENTS
NO IMPROVEMENT	28% PATIENTS

III. DISCUSSION.

Q-Switched Nd:YAG Laser-Tissue Interaction

The laser’s ability to specifically target melanosomes in melanocytes, keratinocytes and melanophages, its ultra-short

pulse width (in nanoseconds) and adjustable spot size are key factors that allow effective targeting of dermal and epidermal pigment (7).

Depth of penetration and selectivity are functions of the wavelength of a laser.

The Q-switched Nd: YAG laser has two wavelengths – a longer wavelength of 1064 nm and a shorter wavelength of 532 nm. The longer wavelength of 1064 nm is ideal for dermal lesions due to its deeper penetration and poor absorption in epidermal melanin(8).

The Q-Switched Nd: YAG Laser (QS- Nd: YAG) can be an alternative treatment option for refractory benign pigmentary lesions. Lasers work on the principle of selective photothermolysis. These lasers have a large spot size up to 10 mm, which also allows deep penetration of the laser beam. Depth of penetration is directly proportional to the spot size of the beam, as more photons are likely to remain within the area(9). To achieve successful outcomes and minimize side effects, it is necessary for the laser to have a “top-hat” beam profile where uniform energy is distributed over a given spot size area without producing undue “hot

spots.” Of late, a fractional handpiece has also become available for some Q-switched Nd: YAG laser systems, wherein the laser beam is split into microbeams, delivering laser energy to a part or fraction of the area treated(10). The fractional handpiece is primarily used for rejuvenation, rhytides and pigmentary conditions such as melasma.

Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation is an acquired pigmentary disorder of the skin that occurs as a result of inflammation induced by various cutaneous diseases or injuries. More than 50% improvement was noticed in 8 % of patients, 25-50% improvement noticed in 45% patients. 24% patients showed slight improvement and no change in pigmentation noticed in 21% patients. Cho and colleagues treated three patients of PIH with QS-Nd: YAG 1064 nm laser at fluences of 1.9–2.6 J/cm² for five sessions and noted good results(11).

Melasma is an acquired pigmentary disorder characterized by brownish hyperpigmented macules on the face. The etiopathogenesis of melasma involves the interplay of various factors such as ultraviolet radiation, hormonal factors (pregnancy and oral contraceptive pills), genetic predisposition, and phototoxic drugs. Q-switched Nd: YAG is the most widely used laser for the treatment of melasma. In our study, 25 - 50% improvement was noted in only 53% of patients. Zhou and colleagues

treated 50 patients of melasma with 1064 nm QS-Nd: YAG laser at low energy levels (fluence of 2.5–3.4 J/cm²) weekly for nine sessions and found 70% of patients had > 50% improvement from baseline(12).

Freckles are small brown macules that appear on sun-exposed areas. Hyperpigmentation is due to an increase in melanin pigment concentration in the melanocytes(13). Five patients with freckles were treated with QS-Nd: YAG laser. One patient had a moderate improvement while 3 patients of slight improvement. Rashid et al. treated 14 patients who complained of freckles with QS Nd: YAG laser (532 nm) for a variable period with an interval of 4-12 weeks. More than 50% improvement was noticed in 10 patients. On follow-up of these patients for 24 months, four showed recurrences(14).

Nevus of Ota is characterized by speckled or mottled coalescing blue-grey pigmentation usually located unilaterally within the distribution of the first and second branches of the trigeminal nerve(13). In the present study, three patients with nevus of Ota had less than 50% improvement and none had 100% clearance. One patient noted mottled hypopigmentation after three sessions of laser treatment. A similar study done by Polnikorn et al. showed good to excellent results in 50% (33/66) of patients who received more than two treatment sessions with QS-Nd: YAG laser (15). Aurangabadkar et al. treated 50 patients of nevus of Ota with Qs Nd: YAG laser and noted > 60% of improvement in 66% of patients, while no patients experienced worsened pigmentation(16).

Lichen planus pigmentosus is characterized by diffuse hyperpigmented dark-brown to slate-grey to black macules present mostly in overexposed areas and flexures(13). Two patients with lichen planus pigmentosus were treated with QS-Nd: YAG laser. None of the patients showed complete clearance of the lesions after three sessions of treatment. Kim et al. reported the complete clearance of pigmentation in a patient with linear lichen planus pigmentosus over the forehead treated with low fluence QS-Nd: YAG (1064 nm) in three weekly sessions combined with 0.1% tacrolimus for a duration of 4 months(17).

The majority of the patients showed at least one score improvement; however, the number of patients showing more

than 75% improvement was less than 10% in all conditions. Satisfactory responses were recorded in cases of PIH and Melasma. Though the degree of improvement was not substantial, the majority of patients were satisfied with even a minor improvement in pigmentation in lesions that had not responded to other modalities.

Our study shows that the QS-Nd: YAG laser can be used with safety as an additional tool in selected cases of refractory pigmentation not responding to other modalities of treatment after proper counselling of the patient with regard to its efficacy.

IV. CONCLUSION

The QS-Nd: YAG laser can be used with safety as an additional tool in the treatment of facial pigmentary conditions refractory to topical treatment. It can be a treatment option in selected cases of refractory pigmentation not responding to other modalities of treatment after proper counselling. Efficacy in clearing pigmentation is partial, variable, and inconsistent. The QS-Nd: YAG laser is effective and worth trying in conditions such as PIH, Melasma and 1 patient of freckles. The response after multiple sessions was variable in Freckles, Naevus of Ota. Adjunctive measures to maintain this response need to be explored in the near future. Few side effects were noticed, all of which resolved without any treatment, for mottled hypopigmentation, topical tacrolimus given. As follow up data was not available, recurrence could not be assessed. The limitations of our study include the small sample size, short-term follow-up, and lack of a control group.

6. REFERENCES

1. Aurangabadkar S, Mysore V. Standard guidelines of care: Lasers for tattoos and pigmented lesions. *Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol* 2009;75 Suppl 2:111-26.
2. Cestari TF, Dantas LP, Boza JC. Acquired hyperpigmentations. *An Bras Dermatol*. 2014;89:11–25.
3. Del Bino S, Duval C, Bernerd F. Clinical and biological characterization of skin pigmentation diversity and its consequences on UV impact. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2018;19:2668.
4. Vashi NA, Wirya SA, Inyang M, et al. Facial hyperpigmentation in skin of color: special considerations and treatment. *Am J Clin Dermatol*. 2017;18:215-30.
5. Darji K, Varade R, West D, et al. Psychosocial impact of postinflammatory hyperpigmentation in patients with acne vulgaris. *J Clin Aesthet Dermatol*. 2017;10:18–23.
6. Pandya A, Berneburg M, Ortonne JP, et al. Guidelines for clinical trials in melasma. *Br J Dermatol*. 2006;156:21-8.
7. Polla LL, Margolis RJ, Dover JS, Whitaker D, Murphy GF, Jacques SL, et al. Melanosomes are a primary target of Q-switched ruby laser irradiation in guinea pig skin. *J Invest Dermatol* 1987;89:281-6.
8. Anderson RR, Margolis RJ, Watanabe S, Flotte T, Hruza GJ, Dover JS, et al. Selective photothermolysis of cutaneous pigmentation by Q-switched Nd:YAG laser pulses at 1064, 532, and 355 nm. *J Invest Dermatol* 1989;93:28-32.
9. Barlow RJ, Hruza GJ. Lasers and light tissue interactions. In: Goldberg DJ, Dover JS, Alam M, editors. *Procedures in Cosmetic Dermatology: Laser and Lights*. 1st ed., Vol. 1. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2005. p. 1-11.
10. Yue B, Yang Q, Xu J, Lu Z. Efficacy and safety of fractional Q-switched 1064-nm neodymium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet laser in the treatment of melasma in Chinese patients. *Lasers Med Sci* 2016;31:1657-63.
11. Cho SB, Park SJ, Kim JS, et al. Treatment of postinflammatory hyperpigmentation using 1064-nm Q-switched Nd:YAG laser with low fluence: report of three cases. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. 2009;23:1026-7.
12. Zhou X, Gold MH, Lu Z, et al. Efficacy and safety of Q-switched 1064 neodymium-doped yttrium aluminum laser treatment of melasma. *Dermatol Surg*. 2011;37:962-70.
13. Khanna N, Rasool S. Facial melanosomes: Indian perspective. *Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol*. 2011;77:552-64.
14. Rashid T, Hussain I, Haider M, et al. Laser therapy of freckles and lentigines with quasi-continuous, frequency-doubled, Nd:YAG (532 nm) laser in Fitzpatrick skin type IV: a 24-month follow-up. *J Cosmet Laser Ther*. 2002;4:81-5.
15. Polnikorn N, Tanrattanakorn S, Goldberg DJ. Treatment of Hori's nevus with the Q-switched Nd:YAG laser. *Dermatol Surg*. 2000; 26:477–80.
16. Aurangabadkar S. QYAG5 Q-switched Nd:YAG laser treatment of nevus of Ota: an Indian study of 50 patients. *J Cutan Aesthet Surg*. 2008;1:80-4.
17. Kim JE, Won CH, Chang S, et al. Linear lichen planus pigmentosus of the forehead treated by neodymium: Yttrium- aluminum-garnet laser and topical tacrolimus. *J Dermatol*. 2012;39:189-91.